

SORSE Workshops: FAIR4RS

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Session 1 Breakout Room 1 Notes

Title: What does interoperability mean for software?

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Participants: all

[IEEE Standard Glossary of Software Engineering Terminology](#)

ability of two or more systems or components to exchange information and to use the information that has been exchanged

[Semantic interoperability](#)

that these exchanges make sense – that the requester and the provider have a common understanding of the ‘meanings’ of the requested services and data.

Add your name and your comments, below:

Q1: What would be a working definition of Interoperability for software?

Level 0: these programs **work together on my computer** in its current state (OS, OS version etc)

Level 1: I can download and install plugins or other **extensions** and they work

Level 2: I can **connect to another computer**/hub (using a downloaded software tool as interface) and work there

Level 3: I can **write my own tools to work with this software** (specifications, APIs et cetera exist for this software)

Level 3.5: API or other programmable interface exists

Level 3.5: A GUI interface exists and allows work (not only browsing/downloading)

Level 3.5: the software I/O uses or converts to standard file formats

Morane: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Interoperability>

“**Interoperability** is a characteristic of a product or system, whose **interfaces** are completely understood, to **work with other products or systems**, at present or in the future, in either implementation or access, without any restrictions” Interoperability in computer science is about working together.

Axel: The piece of software can **read** in **data** in **common formats**, process them, and **output** them in common formats. Ideally, also the program itself can be controlled via a commonly used interface

Paula: software that works with other software, as in **dependencies**. Software that can be **reused** with a different dataset but with a **similar purpose** in mind, for new results. This is more towards interdomain functionality e.g. image analysis from medicine to astronomy.

Stephan:

- Idea: The computer would be able to help me to solve my problem, by **suggesting the right softwares** and their connections with each other .
- No clue: how to formulate this in everyday words, because the problem would need to be explained to the computer

Matthias: The software can **read, process, and write (meta)data** in domain-relevant, community standard formats. The software can **exchange (meta)data** using domain-relevant, community standard APIs.

Fotis: Ensure that the software can be **connected seamlessly in a workflow (and the workflow can be saved, viewed, and reused)**

Carlos: ability of two software systems to **exchange data in a sensible way**. (This could be done, for example, by using standard data exchange formats).

Markus: **Independent** of my own system and computational environment, readable without a specific kind of software (i.e. non-binary, non-proprietary). These aspects are also important for long-term preservation

Anna-Lena: ability of different pieces of software to **exchange data/information** and process them in a meaningful way

Teri: Software that can work **independently** of OS dependencies or workflow requirements. Separation of IO from the actual software algorithm/logic.

Cunliang: **independent** of the OS system and can seamlessly communicate with other software.

Two main themes:

1. Seamless exchange of information
2. Independence to OS

Q2: What is the single most important element of interoperability for software? Which part of interoperability should we follow?

The key point is to not add more levels of complexity to the definition / requirements.

Cunliang: seamless exchange of information

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Matthias: The ability to read, process, and write (meta)data

Anna-Lena: meaningful exchange of information in domain-relevant community standard formats. +(Malin): the ability/process and workhours exist to keep the standard involved up to date and implemented - needs standards committees/working groups and code maintainers

Paula: The environment in which software runs.

Axel: Seamless exchange of information

Teri: exchange of information (for me this would either require standard formats or IO agnostic)

Anna-Lena: meaningful exchange of information

Stephan J.: +1

Carlos: +1

Meaning of exchanged information

Transcribed comments:

<Independence to OS>

- Axel Loewe: While I see the benefit of OS independence, I also think that defining this as a requirement to be FAIR will raise the bar quite a bit for many people and fields to provide FAIR RS.